

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Separation Axioms of $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ – Closed Sets in Topological Spaces

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 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 18-01-2024

Accepted: 12-02-2024

Published: 29-02-2024

Citation: Keerthana KS, Vigneshwaran M, Vidyarani L (2024) Separation Axioms of $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ – Closed Sets in Topological Spaces. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(11): 1028-1035. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i11.135>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: The notion of the article is to introduce new spaces called $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ -space, $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ -space, $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ -space by using $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closed set. **Methods:** The characteristics and properties of the new spaces are explained using theorems and propositions. To prove the converse part of the theorems, counter examples are utilized. **Findings:** As the reverse implications of the theorems which explains the properties of the new spaces, are proved to be not true using the examples we could find the weaker and stronger spaces. Several of their fundamental characterizations and their relationships with other corresponding kinds of spaces are discussed. **Novelty:** The inter relationship between the spaces are identified and investigated and relation among the spaces are graphically illustrated. Independence relation among the $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ -space, $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ -space, $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ -space and other existing spaces are identified. Several examples are discussed for the independence relation.

Keywords: $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - closed set; $b^*g\alpha$ - open set; $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space; $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space; $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space

1 Introduction

R. Devi, H. Maki and K. Balachandran⁽¹⁾ introduced αT_b -space. M. Vigneshwaran and R. Devi⁽²⁾ proposed the idea of $*g\alpha$ -closed sets and studied the properties of $\alpha T^{**1/2}$ -space and TC^{**} -space. M. Vigneshwaran and S. Saranya⁽³⁾ introduced the concepts of $b^*g\alpha$ -closed sets and functions and defined $cT_{b^*g\alpha}$ -spaces and $*bT^{***1/2}$ -spaces based on $b^*g\alpha$ -closed set in topological spaces. Suthi Keerthana K, M. Vigneshwaran and L. Vidyarani⁽⁴⁾ introduced the concepts of $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces.

In this paper, we introduced and study some new spaces by applying $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closed sets, namely $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ -space, $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ -space, $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ -space. Moreover we have studied the properties and characteristics of these spaces with the other existing sets.

2 Preliminaries

The basic definitions, which are used in the next section, are referred from the references⁽¹⁻⁸⁾.

Definition 2.1 : A Subset E of the topological space (S, τ) is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - closed set⁽⁴⁾ if $\alpha cl(E) \subseteq V$ whenever $E \subseteq V$ and V is $b^*g\alpha$ - open in (S, τ) .

Notation: For a space (S, τ) , $C(S, \tau)$ (resp $SC(S, \tau)$, $\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $GC(S, \tau)$, $GSC(S, \tau)$, $GPC(S, \tau)$, $SGC(S, \tau)$, $\alpha GC(S, \tau)$, $G\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $*G\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $GSPC(S, \tau)$, $G^*SPC(S, \tau)$, $G^*C(S, \tau)$, $*\alpha G\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $S^*G\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $P^*G\alpha C(S, \tau)$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau)$) denote the class of all closed (resp. semi- closed, α - closed, g - closed, gs - closed, gp -closed, sg - closed, αg - closed, $g\alpha$ - closed, $*g\alpha$ - closed, gsp - closed, g^*sp - closed, g^* - closed, $*\alpha g\alpha$ - closed, $s^*g\alpha$ - closed. $b^*g\alpha$ - closed, $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - closed) subsets of (S, τ) . CS and OS denote Closed sets and Open sets in topological spaces.

3 Results

Definition 3.1 : A Space (S, τ) is called $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space if every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - closed set is closed.

Theorem 3.2. If (S, τ) is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space, then any singleton of S is either CS or $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS .

Proof: Let $s \in S$ & $\{s\}$ is not CS of (S, τ) . Then S/s is not open.

$\Rightarrow S$ is the only OS containing $s/\{s\}$.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space, S/s is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS or $\{s\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS in (S, τ) .

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.3. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS of $(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$.

$\{f\}$ & $\{h\}$ are $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS , $\{g\}$ is CS but (S, τ) is not $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not CS of (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.4. Any T_b - space is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS .

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is gs - CS & (S, τ) is T_b - space, K is CS .

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.5. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$GSC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space but not T_b - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is gs - CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.6. Any αT_b - space is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS .

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is αg - CS & (S, τ) is αT_b - space, K is CS .

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.7. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$\alpha GC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space but not αT_b - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is αg - CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.8. Any $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space is $\alpha T^{**1/2}$ -space.

Proof: Let K be $*g\alpha$ - CS .

As every $*g\alpha$ - CS is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS , K is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS . Since (S, τ) is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space, K is Closed.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $\alpha T^{**1/2}$ -space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.9. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $\alpha T^{**1/2}$ -space but not $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

$\therefore \{h\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.10. Any semi T1/2- space is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is sg-CS & (S, τ) is semi T1/2- space, K is Closed.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.11. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$SGC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$SC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space but not semi T1/2- space.

$\therefore \{g\}$ is sg- CS but not semi- CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.12. Any $^*\alpha T^{**}1/2$ - space is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $^*\alpha g\alpha$ -CS & (S, τ) is $^*\alpha T^{**}1/2$ - space, K is CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.13. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$^*\alpha G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space but not $^*\alpha T^{**}1/2$ - space.

$\therefore \{g\}$ is $^*\alpha g\alpha$ -CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.14. Any $^*sT^{**}1/2$ - space is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $s^*g\alpha$ -CS & (S, τ) is $^*sT^{**}1/2$ - space, K is CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.15. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$S^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space but not $^*sT^{**}1/2$ - space.

$\therefore \{g\}$ is $s^*g\alpha$ -CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.16. Any $cT_{b^*g\alpha}$ - space is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $b^*g\alpha$ -CS & (S, τ) is $cT_{b^*g\alpha}$ - space, K is CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.17. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space but not $cT_{b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is $b^*g\alpha$ -CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.18. Any pgT_α - space is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

As every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $p^*g\alpha$ -CS & (S, τ) is pgT_α - space, K is CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.19. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$P^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space but not pgT_α - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is $p^*g\alpha$ -CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

The above figure illustrates the relation among $cT_{ab^*g\alpha}$ - space and other existing spaces

Definition 3.20: A Space (S, τ) is called $T_{ab^*g\alpha}^*$ - space if every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is α - CS.

Fig 1. The relation among $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space and other existing spaces

Theorem 3.21. If (S, τ) is $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space, then any singleton of S is either α - CS or $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS.

Proof: Let $s \in S$ & $\{s\}$ is not α - CS of (S, τ) . Then S/s is not α - open.

$\Rightarrow S$ is the only α - OS containing $s/\{s\}$.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ space, S/s is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS or $\{s\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS in (S, τ) .

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.22. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS of $(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$.

$\{f\}$ & $\{h\}$ are $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS, $\{g\}$ is α - CS but (S, τ) is not $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not α - CS of (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.23. Any $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space is $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

Since (S, τ) is $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space, K is Closed. But every CS is α - CS, K is α - closed.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space.

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.24. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space but not $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space.

$\therefore \{h\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not CS in (S, τ) .

Definition 3.25: A Space (S, τ) is called $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space if every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $*g\alpha$ - CS.

Theorem 3.26. If (S, τ) is $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space, then any singleton of S is either $*g\alpha$ - CS or $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS.

Proof: Let $s \in S$ & $\{s\}$ is not $*g\alpha$ - CS of (S, τ) . Then S/s is not $*g\alpha$ - open.

$\Rightarrow S$ is the only $*g\alpha$ - OS containing $s/\{s\}$.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space, S/s is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS or $\{s\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS in (S, τ) .

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.27. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$*g\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS of $(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$

$\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$.

$\{f\}$ & $\{h\}$ are $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - OS, $\{g\}$ is $*g\alpha$ - CS but (S, τ) is not $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space.

$\therefore \{f\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not $*g\alpha$ - CS of (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.28. Any $*\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

But every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $*\alpha g\alpha$ - CS, K is $*\alpha g\alpha$ - CS.

Since (S, τ) is $*\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space, K is $*g\alpha$ - CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.29. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$,

$*\alpha G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space but not $*\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space.

$\therefore \{f, g\}$ is $*\alpha g\alpha$ - CS but not $*g\alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.30. Any $*sT^{***1/2}$ - space is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

But every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $s^*g\alpha$ - CS, K is $s^*g\alpha$ - CS.

Since (S, τ) is $*sT^{***1/2}$ - space, K is $*g\alpha$ - CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.31. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$,

$S^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space but not $*sT^{***1/2}$ - space.

$\therefore \{f, g\}$ is $s^*g\alpha$ - CS but not $*g\alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.32. Any $*bT^{***1/2}$ - space is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

But every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is $b^*g\alpha$ - CS, K is $b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

Since (S, τ) is $*bT^{***1/2}$ - space, K is $*g\alpha$ - CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.33. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,

$B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space but not $*bT^{***1/2}$ - space.

$\therefore \{f, h\}$ is $b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not $*g\alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.34. Any Tc^{**} - space is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

But every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is gs - CS, K is gs - CS.

Since (S, τ) is Tc^{**} - space, K is $*g\alpha$ - CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.35. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, h\}\}$,

$GSC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

(S, τ) is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space but not Tc^{**} - space.

$\therefore \{g, h\}$ is gs - CS but not $*g\alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.36. Any αTc^{**} - space is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space.

Proof: Let K be $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS.

But every $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS is αg - CS, K is αg - CS.

Since (S, τ) is αTc^{**} - space, K is $*g\alpha$ - CS.

$\therefore (S, \tau)$ is $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space

The reverse implication of the theorem need not be true.

Example 3.37. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,

$\alpha GC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

Here (S, τ) is a $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space but not αTc^{**} - space.
 $\therefore \{f, h\}$ is αg - CS but not $*g \alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Fig 2. The relation among $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space and other existing spaces

The above figure illustrates the relation among $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space and other existing spaces

Theorem 3.38. Any $T^*_{ab*g\alpha}$ - space is independent of $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space.

Proof: It can be seen by the following example.

Example 3.39. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}\}$, $*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f, g\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g\}, \{f, g\}\}$.

Here (S, τ) is a $T^*_{ab*g\alpha}$ - space but not $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space,
 $\therefore \{g\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not $*g \alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Example 3.40. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f, g\}\}$, $*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, h\}, \{g, h\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, h\}\}$, $\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}\}$.

Here (S, τ) is a $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space but not $T^*_{ab*g\alpha}$ - space
 $\therefore \{g, h\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not α - CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.41. Any $T^*_{ab*g\alpha}$ - space is independent of $*Tb^*g\alpha$ - space.

Proof: It can be seen by the following example.

Example 3.42. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,
 $G^*C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

Here (S, τ) is a $T^*_{ab*g\alpha}$ - space but not $*Tb^*g\alpha$ - space,
 $\therefore \{g\}$ is $b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not g^* - CS in (S, τ) .

Example 3.43. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$,
 $\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$, $G^*C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$,
 $B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$.

Here (S, τ) is a $*Tb^*g\alpha$ - space but not $T^*_{ab*g\alpha}$ - space,
 $\therefore \{f, h\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not α - CS in (S, τ) .

Theorem 3.44. Any $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space is independent of $*Tb^*g\alpha$ - space.

Proof: It can be seen by the following example.

Example 3.45. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$,
 $G^*C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{f, g\}\}$, $B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$.

Here (S, τ) is a $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - space but not $*Tb^*g\alpha$ - space,
 $\therefore \{g\}$ is $b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not g^* - CS in (S, τ) .

Example 3.46. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, g\}, \{f, h\}\}$,

$*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$, $G^*C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$,
 $B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{g, h\}\}$.
 Here (S, τ) is a $*Tb^*g\alpha$ - space but not $*g\alpha T^{***1/2}$ - space,
 $\therefore \{f, g\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not $*g\alpha$ - CS in (S, τ) .

Fig 3. Diagram illustrates the independence among the defined spaces

The above diagram illustrates the independence among the defined spaces

Theorem 3.47. $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space is independent of T_c - space and αT_c - space.

Proof: It can be seen by the following example.

Example 3.48. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f\}, \{f, g\}\}$,
 $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{g, h\}\}$, $\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{h\}, \{g, h\}\}$,
 $G^*C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, h\}\}$,
 $GSC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{h\}, \{g\}, \{g, h\}, \{f, h\}\} = \alpha C(S, \tau)$.

Here (S, τ) is a $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space but not T_c - space and αT_c - space.

$\therefore \{g\}$ is gs - CS and αg - CS but not g^* - CS in (S, τ) .

Example 3.49. Let $S = \{f, g, h\}$, $\tau = \{S, \phi, \{f, h\}\}$, $\alpha B^*G\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$, $\alpha C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}\}$, $G^*C(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\}$, $GSC(S, \tau) = \{S, \phi, \{g\}, \{f, g\}, \{g, h\}\} = \alpha C(S, \tau)$. Here (S, τ) is a T_c - space and αT_c - space but not $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space,

Fig 4. The red line indicates the relationship between the separation axioms of $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - Closed Set and other existing spaces

$\therefore \{f, g\}$ is $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - CS but not α - CS in (S, τ)

In the above diagram, the red line indicates the relationship between the separation axioms of $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - Closed Set and other existing spaces but not conversely and the blue line indicates the independence among the spaces.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we have introduced the separations axioms using $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - Closed Set in topological spaces and examined the properties and characteristics of $cT_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - space, $T_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}^*$ - space, $*g\alpha T^{***}_{1/2}$ - Space by using $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - closed set and comparison of the defined spaces with other existing spaces. In future, the article can be extended to find the compactness and connectedness properties of $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ - Closed Set in topological spaces.

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